

SCIENTISTS' OPINIONS ABOUT GENDER THEORY

Khaydarova Nigora

Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages,
Senior teacher of the Department of
Theoretical Aspects of the English Language
Sarkor2019@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10430346>

Abstract: This article deals with related theories of gender studies and linguistics, which are the subject of intense debate among contemporary linguistics scholars. Based on the opinion of scientists, gender differences in speech and language create gender stereotypes that arise from the social roles of men and women and influence the self-determination of a person's gender according to sociocultural principles and norms. The basis for the formation of gender stereotypes is the concepts of femininity and masculinity, which later underwent serious changes, expressing the contradiction between a person's biological sex and the psychological manifestations of gender.

Key words: gender, theory, man, woman, cultural principles, stereotype, femininity, masculinity

TO COME IN

International nations have been at the forefront of gender issues research in recent decades. These studies shed light on an individual's social, linguistic, and cultural traits in addition to their biological makeup. Gender is defined as a collection of socio-psychological processes and cultural factors that impact a person's speech patterns and behavior choices. Gender stereotypes are produced by gendered language and speech differences. These stereotypes stem from the social roles that men and women play in society and have an impact on how each individual determines their gender by the sociocultural norms, values, and laws that govern this community.

The notions of femininity and masculinity, which subsequently underwent significant modifications, served as the foundation for the development of gender stereotypes. They symbolized the discrepancy between an individual's psychological gender expressions and their biological sex.

Gender is the most overt oppositional sign in the human classification. How does this opposition manifest itself in language, which is both a form and an expression of human worldview? L.N. Pushkareva claims that while ancient scientists also considered the relationship between grammatical gender and biological gender, the idea of grammatical gender (*genus*) was long accepted as a natural phenomenon, with male and female gender (*nar* and *moda*) existing for a considerable amount of time, including the Middle Ages, those who think it is intrinsically related to development. The notions of femininity and masculinity, which subsequently underwent significant modifications, served as the foundation for the development of gender stereotypes. They symbolized the discrepancy between an individual's psychological gender. As a result, they held that the nouns of the feminine root represent words associated with passivity, weakness, dreaminess, and sinfulness, whereas the names of the masculine root reflect strength, energy, enthusiasm, and activity. Subsequently, however,

languages were found in which there was no linguistic differentiation of gender at all, or in which there were distinct linguistic variants known as "muzskoy rod" and "zhensky rod." As a result, the gender category of nouns is currently regarded as a purely linguistic category, meaning that it is a class of words with particular adaptation features and the ability to accept certain agreement suffixes. Male and female are the two concepts of "gender" that exist in language and consciousness in addition to muzhskoy and jensky rod. This is limited to organisms. Gender is a biological phenomenon that exists outside of human volition. It is two categories of nouns that indicate living things: male and female in humans and male and female in animals.[11]

MAIN PART

According to A. V. Kirilina, the word "gender" was borrowed into the study of social philosophy, sociology, anthropology, history, and political discourse from linguistics (from the category of English gender - grammatical root). Since this concept is linked to natural determinism as well as biological differences between men and women, the unequal division of labor between the sexes, and societal attitudes toward men and women, a comparison with the term "sexus" (sex) - biological sex - was made.[12]

What is the history of this idea in relation to societal needs? N.A. Blokhina links the idea of gender to the advancement of civilization, stating that a shift in gender norms has resulted in the ability for an individual, such as a man, to assume the gender role of a woman in society (men looking after children to the family).[1] I.I. Bulichev claims that the social divisions between the sexes date back to prehistoric times: "In prehistoric culture, gender (social sex) and sex (biological sex) were kept apart. The gender panorama of reality in the early phases of the origin of society and the emergence of humanity may or may not match to the pure biological traits of men and women as feminine and masculine ways of existing. When it comes to gender identity, a husband or wife's real social connection matters more than the concept of gender as determined by science. This demonstrates how social gender is a (non-biological) gender that exists independently. This shows the independent nature of social gender as a (non-biological) gender.[2]

The majority of foreign writers stand out for their understanding of the implicit gender connection in women's history that feminist theorists have established. The notion that women's history updated and supplemented the history of gender or the sexes was heavily stressed in the early studies of the 1980s. A distinct border between these directions started to emerge in later research. This is most likely a result of the gendered history of some independence and the scholarly community's acceptance of it.

The feminist movement in science known as "women's history" aims to separate "women's history" from "men's history." Scholars such as S. Ortner, M. Devin, and M. Rosaldo have attempted to illustrate the historical role of women. Throughout the process, scientific impartiality was frequently compromised: the need to demonstrate how equally important men and women have always been led to the falsification of data.[3]

According to feminist theory, patriarchy rules society and all texts and discursive processes instill patriarchal, or masculine, ideals in people.

DISCUSSIONS/RESULTS

Women's studies was the precursor to gender studies. Gender studies includes both male and female subjects, in contrast to women's studies. The core of gender studies is the examination of gender differences and similarities, mainly as seen through the lenses of socio-

psychological and socio-cultural aspects of gender, if the aim of women's studies is to study just women.[10]

Gender, women's lives and circumstances, and men's relationships with women are all topics of study in feminist studies. The research method is radicalized in feminist studies, which is one of its defining characteristics. It is not evident that gender studies are politically charged. The idea of "gender" later made its way into the study of linguistics. Regarding the subject of gender as a mental structure, Western science has not yet come to a consensus. In other words, a scientific definition that clarifies the sociocultural roles of gender and permits these roles to be distinguished from social or biological constructions. In the second instance, gender encompasses a minimum of four categories of traits: biological sex, gender-role identity, gender-role norms, and gender-role stereotypes." The final three traits are occasionally referred to as "gender display" in American sociologists' writings, which is based on the different ways that "cultural components of gender"—stereotypes and socialization and identification strategies created by society based on gender norms—show up. Hoffmann is the source of this term.[10]

Every year, more and more scholars are focusing on this problem. Gender studies in Uzbekistan undoubtedly have unique features. Studies that are gender-neutral predominate when describing language units in Uzbek linguistics. This is due to several factors. This has to do, among other things, with the Uzbek language's lack of specific gender-specific categories, the traditional attention to gender differences in both Uzbek and gender-indicative linguistics, and the relatively new directions in applied linguistics. The word "gender" itself is new to our language; before its formation and complex use traditions, it was not in use. In this regard, our gender studies will inevitably have their characteristics. Gender orientations were formed in foreign linguistics, on the one hand, stereotypes of femininity and masculinity, as well as gender asymmetry, were recorded in the language, and on the other hand, specific features of speech behavior of men and women began to be studied.

Since the second half of the last century, interest in gender studies in the humanities has increased. It was a demand made by the most prosperous era in known human history. According to the United Nations Development Program, the components of human development include effective work, empowerment of people opportunities for participation in decision-making on issues related to public life, sustainable development, and equality of opportunities and choices for all people.[3]

Although research in this direction has not lost its novelty in Uzbek linguistics, it cannot be denied that there is significant research in this regard. In particular, among several studies created in Uzbek linguistics in recent years, prof. The works of S. Mominov have a special place.[6] In his research, he was able to reveal the specific aspects of Uzbek speech communication with men and women with vivid examples.[4]

The reason for the lameness of Uzbek gender linguistics comes from these factors. Despite the great interest in all areas of applied linguistics in recent years, it is still too early to say that research in this field is conducted as a system. But not only interest in this field, but also socio-economic need has ripened.

"There has never been a time in the history of mankind when the socio-economic conditions set science as many tasks as it is now. Today, specific tasks are being set before the humanities, and specific deadlines for solving these tasks are being set. Failure to fulfill this

requirement may lead to a certain subject being deprived of its object and subject and becoming a component of other subjects.[5]

CONCLUSION

In linguistics, gender is a category whose study was initially associated with the spread of feminism as a social movement and the spread of postmodernism as a scientific paradigm, but after a few decades, gender studies transcended these directions and became interdisciplinary studies at the intersection of linguistics, sociology, history, and other disciplines. became a field.

There is no uniformity in the definition of the concept of "gender", but most scientists tend to see the role of gender and social role in the formation of stereotypes of behavior (including communication behavior). In modern life, "gender" is indirectly related to a person's biological sex.

References:

1. Blokhina N.A. The concept of gender: formation, basic concepts and ideas // Society and gender. – Ryazan: AVG, 2003. – P.302.
2. Bulychev I.I. Images of masculinity and femininity in the format of a gender picture of the world // Credo, No. 1, 2004.- P.45.
3. Gender basics: theory and practice. - Tashkent: 2003. - B.9
4. Mominov S. Gender characteristics of Uzbek communication // Uzbek language and literature, 1999. No. 5. - B. 64-66.;
5. Shahobiddinova Sh. Theses of applied linguistics. - ADU. Scientific Bulletin, 2016, No. 3 - B.79-80.
6. Iskandarova Sh. Communicative forms of the Uzbek speech habit: Philology. science. name ... diss. - Samarkand, 1993. - 140 p.
7. Mominov S. Socio-linguistic features of Uzbek communication behavior: Philology. science. d-ri ... diss. - Tashkent, 2000. - 236 p.;
8. Kakharov Q. Comparative study of Uzbek and German speech etiquette: Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) diss. - Andijan, 2020. - 148 p.
9. Pushkareva N.L. Woman. Gender. Culture. – M.: Terra, 1998. – B.18.
10. <https://konspekt.com/referat-24215-doklad-gendernye-issledovaniya-v-zarubezhnoj-i-rossijskoj-lingvistike>.
11. Pushkareva N.L. Woman. Gender. Culture. – M.: Terra, 1998. – B.19.
12. Kirilina A.V. Some results of gender research in Russian linguistics // Gender: Language, Culture, Communication. Materials of the Third International Conference. – M., 2003.– P. 12.
13. <https://libr.link/knigi-pedagogika/soderjanie-otlichie-ponyatiy-gendernye-75689.html>;
14. <http://www.med24info.com/books/gendernaya-terapiya-spravochnik-prakticheskogo-psihologa/gendernye-issledovaniya-15741.html>;
15. <https://arzamas.academy/materials/959>